

This statistics shows the number of Simulink blocks being used in our case study:

- * ADAS_v01: Advanced Driver Assistance System version 1
- * ADAS_v02: Advanced Driver Assistance System version 2
- * ADAS_v03: Advanced Driver Assistance System version 3
- * ADAS_v04: Advanced Driver Assistance System version 4
- * ALS: Adaptive Light System

The output of this table was generated with the Matlab command: `sldiagnostics(<model name>, 'CountBlocks')`

We made the following small changes:

1) added the line *Blocks (not counting port blocks)* to this table for comparison reasons.

This number is Total blocks minus all port blocks (the one with the *)

2) add the line *Ports (also counting ports of atomic blocks)* to this table for comparison reasons.

This number was created by a MATLAB script counting also the input and output ports of atomic blocks such as *AND*

3) highlighted cells to make comparisons for transformations to C&C models more comprehensible

4) added * at block names which are close to ports in our C&C model definition

Key

Numbers are in Paper

Blocks which increase size of C&C model

Blocks which increase size of C&C model only in combination with Enabled or Triggered Port

Blocks which decrease size of C&C model

comment

Blocks marked with a * are actually ports (main purpose is to send or receive data);

TargetLink Blocks are not marked again since they are already counted as Simulink Blocks

(TargetLink blocks are masked Simulink blocks)

	<u>ADAS_v01</u>	<u>ADAS_v02</u>	<u>ADAS_v03</u>	<u>ADAS_v04</u>	<u>ALS</u>
Blocks (not counting port blocks)	327	686	664	655	1065
Ports (also counting ports of atomic blocks)	701	1454	1480	1513	2753
Total blocks	550	1050	1030	1044	1643
ActionPort *	5	11	14	11	10
BusCreator	10	14	19	20	22
BusSelector	13	15	20	27	25
Constant	56	124	141	135	252
DataStoreMemory	2	2	2	2	0
DataStoreRead	7	10	10	8	0
DataStoreWrite	9	19	19	15	0
DataTypeConversion	0	0	1	1	0
Demux	0	0	0	1	1
DiscreteStateSpace	1	1	1	1	0
Display	5	5	8	8	0
EnablePort *	4	3	3	6	0
From	0	0	0	0	52
Gain	5	3	11	10	25
Goto	0	0	0	0	52
If	3	4	5	5	4
Inport *	119	192	197	216	277
Logic	25	95	45	43	96
Lookup	1	1	1	1	0
Lookup_n-D	1	2	7	9	1
M-S-Function	1	1	1	1	25
ManualSwitch	5	5	9	8	11
Math	0	4	4	4	0
Memory	2	1	1	1	1
Merge	2	2	3	3	4
MinMax	1	2	3	4	8
MultiPortSwitch	0	0	1	1	0
Output *	86	139	133	141	291
Product	1	1	10	14	28
RelationalOperator	14	23	41	39	64
Saturate	2	3	3	6	0
Scope	0	0	0	0	24
Stateflow	0	0	0	1	1
SubSystem	122	211	203	195	184
Sum	7	23	24	23	20
Switch	14	57	41	41	87

	Terminator	8	14	11	12	43
	<i>TriggerPort *</i>	9	19	19	15	0
	UniformRandomNumber	1	1	1	1	0
	<i>UnitDelay</i>	9	43	18	15	35
M	ACT_SG_V200_False	5	5	5	4	11
M	ACT_SG_V200_SysInit	1	3	1	1	1
M	ACT_SG_V200_True	5	5	5	4	11
M	Compare To Zero	2	2	2	2	0
M	Discrete Transfer Function with Initial States	1	1	1	1	0
M	MIL Subsystem	1	1	1	1	1
M	MSR_V200_AccumulatorResetEnabledLimited	0	0	1	1	0
M	MSR_V200_Limit	0	0	1	1	0
M	SL_ACT_SG_VAPSRealTimeTimer_V100	1	1	1	1	1
M	SL_ACT_SG_VAPS_TimeConfiguration_V100	1	1	1	1	1
M	Slider Gain	2	2	6	6	5
M	TLACT_SG_V200_False	4	18	6	5	15
M	TLACT_SG_V200_SysInit	2	4	4	3	0
M	TLACT_SG_V200_True	1	1	1	1	7
M	TLMSR_V200_CountDownResetEnabled	0	4	2	1	0
M	TLMSR_V200_EdgeFalling	1	4	1	1	4
M	TLMSR_V200_EdgeRising	2	12	3	3	3
M	TLMSR_V200_RSFlipFlop	2	8	3	3	8
M	TLMSR_V200_StopWatchResetEnabled	0	0	0	0	2
M	TLMSR_V200_TimerResetEnabled	0	0	0	0	2
M	TLMSR_V200_TimerResetEnabledMemory	0	0	0	0	6
M	TLMSR_V200_TimerRetriggerResetEnabled	0	0	0	0	1
M	TL_Constant	25	93	98	85	164
M	<i>TL_DataStoreMemory</i>	2	2	2	2	0
M	<i>TL_DataStoreRead</i>	7	10	10	8	0
M	<i>TL_DataStoreWrite</i>	9	19	19	15	0
M	<i>TL_Enable</i>	1	1	1	1	1
M	TL_Gain	2	0	3	2	2
M	TL_Inport	8	8	14	13	25
M	TL_LogicalOperator	23	93	40	38	89
M	TL_Lookup1D	1	2	7	9	1
M	TL_Math	0	4	4	4	0
M	TL_Merge	2	2	3	3	4
M	TL_MinMax	1	2	3	4	8
M	TL_MultiPortSwitch	0	0	1	1	0
M	TL_Outport	5	6	8	8	24
M	TL_Product	0	0	7	11	21
M	TL_RelationalOperator	6	14	30	27	54
M	TL_Saturate	1	2	2	5	0
M	TL_SimFrame	1	1	1	1	1
M	TL_Sum	5	21	20	19	17
M	TL_Switch	8	51	31	30	78
M	<i>TL_UnitDelay</i>	7	39	15	12	34
M	VERSION_INFO_BLOCK	27	43	49	48	24